

The Symbiocene as a transformative vision to overcome the degenerative mindset of the Anthropocene

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Abstract

We live in times of crises and calls for a transformative social-ecological change are voiced increasingly often. The question is, however, how such a transformation could be achieved. The prevailing view is that we are living in an era in which human activities significantly altered planet Earth: the Anthropocene. According to this narrative, humans are a very powerful force, turning the global situation to the worse. It has been argued that this view can cause disillusion and frustration, thus hampering the willingness to change the situation. With this contribution, we explore the potential of the recently suggested concept of a Symbiocene as a transformation vision able to stimulate action. At the core of the concept, we see a call for renewed human-nature relationships, and we discuss how current changes in the conception of nature, humans and their relationships can be utilized as scaffoldings for the conception of a Symbiocene. We explore how to move from an economy-centred thinking with degenerative environmental effects to a planet-centred thinking with regenerative effects, and suggest that sensory-triggered experiences, induced by interactions with nature and arts, are key for achieving this transition.

1. Introduction

We live in times of crises. Biodiversity loss is happening at increasing rates, on a global scale as well locally (IPBES, 2019), and effects of climate change already have serious impacts on everyday life in many regions of the world. These interlinked crises are the expression and the effect of many interdependent global changes that started happening during the beginning of the 20th century (Steffen et al., 2011). Since the year 2000, the term ‘Anthropocene’ has been widely used to describe this period of time, in which the effects of human activities on Earth’s geology and ecosystems intensified strongly. While the official scientific approval of an Anthropocene as geological epoch following the Holocene, proven by observable, significant differences in geological layers, has not been approved, the term and the underlying considerations have nevertheless had profound impact on societal debates. It became the core of a new narrative, bringing to light how severely and significantly human activities have already altered the planet (Ellis, 2018). The concept of the Anthropocene thus

carries with it the devastating message that human activities have caused severe and lasting changes everywhere on the planet, from mountain tops to deep sea, from the arctic to the tropics, reaching even the remotest places on earth. In the story of the Anthropocene, humans are a bad influence, turning the situation on planet Earth to the worse. Such a misanthropic mindset in combination with the feeling that the current situation is ‘beyond repair’ could cause disillusion and frustration, hampering the willingness to try changing the situation (Ellis et al., 2025).

This observation has led the philosopher Glenn Albrecht to suggest that what is really needed to create momentum for the urgently needed transformative social-ecological change is a positive vision of an age beyond the Anthropocene (Albrecht, 2016). Given the radical societal changes needed to stop the biodiversity and climate crises, the goal of ending the Anthropocene may be much more appropriate than merely striving to improve it. Also, if the anthropocentric worldview is a root cause of the crises, the only way to achieve improvement must be to overcome it, which means that an entirely new narrative is needed. Albrecht’s suggestion in this regard is the ‘Symbiocene’.

According to Glenn Albrecht, “[t]he Symbiocene will be that period in Earth’s history where humans symbiotically reintegrate themselves, emotionally, psychologically and technologically, into nature and natural systems.” (Albrecht, 2014) p. 58. The core of the idea of a Symbiocene, at least in our reading of the concept, is that it will be an era in which enriched, renewed human-nature relationships prevail.

The term Symbiocene suggests a tight conceptual connection to the biological term ‘symbiosis’ (from Greek *συμβίωσις*, *symbiōsis*, "living together"). In biology, a symbiosis is a close and long-lasting interaction between two organisms belonging to two different biological species. While in common language the term tends to carry the meaning of mutually beneficial, harmonious togetherness, actual symbioses of two organisms ‘living together’ in fact can take the form of a constant, ongoing struggle for resources (Sanders, 2023). In this sense, biological symbiosis seems to be a useful metaphor, since constant searches for good compromises in human-nature relationships would have to be an integral part of a Symbiocene as well (see e.g. Gao et al., 2023).

The contextual, overarching idea of a Symbiocene as an era with enhanced, renewed human-nature relationships can be inspiring in itself. However, much conceptual work is needed to fill it with deeper meaning. Only as a rich concept will it be able to allow for the development of concrete and tangible ideas for the future, and realistic steps for getting there. Related approaches, reflecting on our role, responsibilities and possibilities as humans, on the concept of ‘nature’, and on humans’ relationship to, responsibility for, and action in ‘nature’ abound, and we will pick up some of these in the upcoming paragraphs. We neither aim at a complete review of related work, nor do we attempt to merge the ones we picked into a unified, coherent philosophy. Rather, we would like to propose each of these approaches as having the potential to conceptually enrich the idea of a Symbiocene, and thus as potential starting points for adding an inner scaffolding to the outer shell of this promising concept. We regard these approaches as ‘good to think with’ (Garber, 2008) when moving towards a Symbiocene.

In the following, we will first develop our suggestions for how existing approaches in the humanities, philosophy and environmental ethics could be used as conceptual backing for the concept of the Symbiocene. We will then introduce our conception of the Symbiocene as a transformative vision leading from economy-centred thinking with degenerative effects to

plant-centred thinking with regenerative effects. Finally, we will explore how sensory-triggered experiences with nature and arts could be utilized as levers for inducing this transition.

2. Human-nature relationships in the Symbiocene

Since renewed human-nature relationships are at the heart of the concept of a Symbiocene, it is necessary to go into detail with three key questions: ‘what is human?’, ‘what is nature?’ and ‘how do they relate to each other?’. The following chapters will address these three key questions by describing the challenges and complexities they contain, and by offering brief descriptions of approaches and concepts that we consider helpful for developing an encompassing, transformative vision of a Symbiocene.

2.1 What is human?

The question ‘what is human?’ is at the core of humanity’s search for meaning and has therefore been addressed for ages. Consequently, various and quite diverse answers have been proposed. Western thinking, however, has for a long time been dominated by the humanistic ideal, regarding ‘Man’ as the universal measure of all things. Anthropocentrism was the dominating worldview, regarding human beings (especially white males) as exceptional, and as largely autonomous and self-sufficient.

This view is beginning to give way to other conceptions of what is human, and what is the relationship of humans to non-human beings and non-living things. Insights from diverse fields of research contribute to this development. For example, there is good reason to argue that the human body is not entirely human in itself, because there is a multitude of microorganisms populating our skin and intestines, and possibly even our brains (Servick, 2018). These organisms have been shown to have immense effects on human physiology (Rackaityte & Lynch, 2020), and they very likely even affect human emotions and social behaviour (Smith & Wissel, 2019). Being human thus means to be closely entangled and strongly depending on other living beings (Sheldrake, 2020; Tsing, 2015), even inside our bodies.

Moreover, many technical advancements can be interpreted as extensions to the human body. Smartphones have almost become part of the modern human, as technological extensions of the brain. On a more general level, a main difference between human and non-human animals is the ability to produce and utilize artifacts, qualifying the human as a being closely entangled with the things it produces. Colomina and Wigley (2016) consequently argue: *“What makes the human human is not inside the body or brain, or even inside the collective social body, but in our interdependency with artifacts. [...] In a sense, the artifacts are more human than the human”* (p. 23-24).

Overall, a mindset is currently forming that regards humans as much less independent and self-sufficient than suggested by Anthropocentrism and the previously prevailing humanistic view. Taking into account in addition the current upsurge of voices against Eurocentric humanistic superiority, a ‘Posthumanism’ has been called for, aiming for a fundamental re-conception of what is human. As Rosi Braidotti proposes, *“the posthuman knowing subject has to be understood as a relational embodied and embedded, affective and accountable entity”* (Braidotti (2019) p. 31; but see Hoppe and Lemke (2021) for a warning against

Posthumanism). Focusing on the close entanglement of the human body with non-human organisms as well as with artifacts, emphasizing the dependencies of humans rather than their independence, and accounting for the multiple and diverse views on ‘what is human’ could have the power to trigger a humbler mindset and a sense of both dependence and responsibility. These are indispensable preconditions for a transition towards a Symbiocene.

2.2 What is nature?

Corresponding to the view of ‘Man’ as dominant force and universal measure of things, the conception of ‘nature’ as the pristine, untouched and wild has prevailed in Western thinking for a long time (Inkpen, 2017). Consequently, pristine nature constituted the core and main goal of nature conservation (Mace, 2014), with a main focus on preventing human activities from ‘spoiling’ and degrading nature.

This view is currently being challenged as well. One of the triggers for this development is the observation that ecosystems consisting mainly of non-native species and inhabiting strongly altered soils (so called ‘novel ecosystems’) can thrive just as well as their ‘natural’ counterparts (Hobbs et al., 2006). The resulting question is: Can such ecosystems be regarded as ‘nature’ as well, and might they even be worth protecting (Marris, 2011; Pearce, 2015)? As a second challenge to the idea of ‘nature’ as ‘the pristine’, traces of human-induced transformation have been discovered even in remote and seemingly untouched ecosystems like the Amazon rainforest. Such discoveries reinforced the argument that ‘pristine nature’ and ‘wilderness’ are cultural constructions that urgently need to be called into question (Casetta, 2023; Marris, 2011). Consequently, instead of idealizing nature as the pristine and untouched, New Conservationists allow it to be a ‘rambunctious garden’ and thus wild and managed at the same time (Marris, 2011). The goal of nature conservation in this view is no longer some long-lost state of ‘pristineness’, but instead historic states are used as guidelines to orient conservation and restoration efforts towards enhancing nature in diverse forms and appearances (Higgs et al., 2018; Kareiva, 2014; Kareiva et al., 2012).

Environmental ethicist Vogel (2015) goes one step further and suggests dropping the term ‘nature’ altogether, because it carries with it the notion of something outside and independent of humans. He argues that humans cannot exist without changing nature, because they need to consume, dispose and build in order to live. Is the outcome of such interaction of humans with nature not nature anymore, then? Does everything humans touch turn into something artificial? An approach that may allow keeping the terms ‘nature’ and ‘natural’ while accounting for many of the just mentioned challenges is to think about naturalness as a matter of degree (Casetta, 2020; Deplazes-Zemp, 2022). The philosopher Elena Casetta suggests using *independence from human intervention* as criterion for grading naturalness (Casetta, 2020): The less the identity conditions and the survival of an environmental object (e.g. a place, like a specific wetland) depend on human intervention, the more natural it is. Environmental ethicist Anna Deplazes-Zemp suggests, along similar lines, to regard ‘natural’ and ‘artificial’ as terms describing one’s own relationship to nature (Deplazes-Zemp, 2022). For us as human beings, there should be a difference between things we have purposefully designed, and things that came about without our intentional involvement.

These examples of current work on the conception of nature demonstrate that concerning the question ‘what is nature’, a new mindset begins to form as well, corresponding to the new conception of ‘what is human’. The old view of ‘nature’ as something independent and apart from humans, from the artificial, or from culture, and the view of ‘nature’ as a normative

guideline, are more and more often regarded as no longer helpful (Casetta, 2020; Deplazes-Zemp, 2022; Friedman et al., 2022; Vogel, 2015).

2.3. Embracing the entanglement: From an anthropocentric to a relational worldview

Coming from both sides - 'human' and 'nature' - seems to lead to the conclusion that the question of how both are related is a precondition for defining either. As indicated above, the question of how humans relate to nature has been answered in the Western tradition in line with the prevailing modernist mindset: 'Man' is the dominant force, and nature is something altogether different and can be formed and used to satisfy needs (West et al., 2020).

According to this worldview, nature and culture appear as strictly separated (Beery et al., 2023; Descola, 2013). Nature in its 'pure' form is either to be subdued (e.g. cultivated) and utilized as a resource, or to be conserved and protected from the influence of human activities. This worldview, along with its capitalist and imperialist manifestations, has often been suggested as being the root cause of the current climate and biodiversity crises (Blom, 2022; Friedman et al., 2022; Leibenath et al., 2021).

More recently and especially in the context of the development of sustainability science, a worldview has formed that leaves behind the modernist approach, and conceives humans, non-human organisms, and other objects in nature as components of complex coupled systems. Interactions between these 'social' and 'ecological' entities produce emergent outcomes. Societal transformation towards more sustainability requires, according to this mindset, full recognition of the interdependence of humans and nature across all societal spheres. Here, nature and culture are no longer regarded as a strict dichotomy, but rather as dualism. There is awareness of the fact that human beings are connected to nature in diverse ways, and that they have some kind of responsibility towards nature, but still, due to their cognitive abilities, humans are regarded as outstanding and separate (West et al., 2020).

This complex coupled systems approach seems an important step towards accounting for the close entanglement of humans and nature. However, since according to that paradigm, humans and nature are connected but still separate entities, the challenges pointed out above remain. What is a human if we must think of it as something distinct from nature? Where can we find nature today if we regard it as something unaffected by humans? How can we categorize entities in environmental systems as either social or ecological, either cultural or natural, when in fact they tend to be both at the same time? To overcome these challenges, it has been argued, we need a relational paradigm, according to which humans and nature are viewed as existing in combination only, reciprocally constituting each other through their relations (Haraway, 2016; Raymond et al., 2022; Tsing, 2015). Relational approaches have been formulated in diverse contexts, reviewed e.g. in Hoppe and Lemke (2021) and West et al. (2020). In the following, we will select a few of these approaches which we consider especially helpful for enriching the vision of a Symbiocene, focusing first on ontological suggestions and next on an ethical application.

2.3.1 Relationship as key to understanding the world: Relational ontologies

During the past two centuries, the cultural and social sciences have seen a remarkable process of reorientation and shift in focus. Increasingly, the ability of humans to assert full control over societal and other processes is called into question. New theories are forming according to which not only humans can affect and steer processes, but also other 'objects'. Especially,

matter is no longer understood as a simple, inert and passive object but is rather characterized by some kind of ‘stubbornness’, having agency as well. Matter, and thus also non-human beings and non-living things, can be active actors that affect human beings. (Hoppe & Lemke, 2021)

Along with this notion comes the idea that the interacting entities (humans, non-human beings and other ‘objects’) do not pre-exist in a ‘pure’ version prior to any interaction, but instead, the interactions themselves are constitutive for any given entity. Gaining understanding of the world thus no longer means to scrutinize single elements that make up society or the environment, but instead it means to focus on the relations between these elements and to analyse how these relations shape them. Relational ontologies thus focus on processes instead of states, and on interactions leading to co-constitution and co-evolution. (Hoppe & Lemke, 2021)

Quite prominent among these approaches is Bruno Latour’s Actor-Network Theory. It posits that everything in the social and natural worlds, meaning human as well as non-human entities including non-living things, interact in transient networks of relationships (Latour, 2005). The theory builds on the premise of general symmetry, meaning that there is no inherent, pre-existing difference between the entities that interact in a network - there is thus also no principal difference between ‘natural’ and ‘cultural’ entities, or ‘humans’ and ‘non-humans’. Further, Latour (1993) posits that things or phenomena we encounter are often hybrids between nature and culture. Western thinking usually divides the world into two groups – nature versus culture, humans versus non-humans – but at the same time, in daily lives, it is constantly hybrids between those two groups that must be dealt with. He suggests facing this dilemma by creating a Parliament of Things, in which humans and non-humans, including hybrids, interact on equal terms (Latour, 1993).

The idea that relations are constitutive has also been applied with regards to the entanglement of humans and different aspects of nature. Donna Haraway, as one of the most influential writers in this area, states: “[B]eings constitute each other and themselves. Beings do not preexist their relatings. [...] The world is a knot in motion. Biological and cultural determinism are both instances of misplaced concreteness—i.e., the mistake of, first, taking provisional and local category abstractions like ‘nature’ and ‘culture’ for the world and, second, mistaking potent consequences to be preexisting foundations. There are no pre-constituted subjects and objects, and no single sources, unitary actors, or final ends.” (Haraway, 2003, p. 6). In her view, it is not pre-existing entities that interact in networks, but rather, the world consists of “*intra-active entities-in-assemblages*” (Haraway, 2015) in which entities come into being only in and through relationships (Hoppe & Lemke, 2021).

2.3.2 Appreciating the significance of human-nature relationships: Relational values

Relational ontologies like the ones briefly described in the previous paragraphs propose shifting the focus from entities (e.g., humans, non-human things in nature) to relations. The question arises what such a shift would mean for environmental ethics and nature conservation. One of the goals of environmental ethics is to provide philosophically grounded and consistent lines of arguments for why to protect or care for nature. For a long time, the field has been dominated by two seemingly opposing opinions concerning which kinds of values can be assigned to nature and biodiversity. On the one hand, it has been (and still is) argued that nature is to be protected because it has value for humans (i.e., because of its

instrumental value). According to this view, biodiversity contributes to ecosystem functions and services, and these in turn benefit human wellbeing (e.g., Millennium Ecosystem Assessment, 2005). An alternative line of argument states that nature has value in itself: an *intrinsic value* that exists independent of humans and their judgements (Callicott, 1986; Piccolo, 2017).

Recently, it is increasingly recognized that in face of the biodiversity crisis, instead of pitching these two lines of argumentation against each other, it is much more helpful to appreciate that different (groups of) people can assign diverse and differing values to nature (value pluralism, Díaz et al., 2015; Pascual et al., 2017; Tallis & Lubchenco, 2014). Further, an increasing number of authors in environmental ethics and beyond argue that it is useful to add a third category to the previous two. In addition to instrumental and intrinsic values, it should be considered that nature can also have *relational values* (Chan et al., 2016; IPBES, 2023; Pascual et al., 2017). Here, the value lies in the relationship humans have with natural entities or nature in a broader sense, e.g., symbolic meaning, cultural identification or feelings of kin and stewardship (Chan et al., 2016). Building on this, some authors point to related notions of ‘*care*’ prevalent in indigenous worldviews and (eco-)feminist theories (Jax et al., 2018), and to the need of enabling people to become part of conservation decisions (Dotson & Pereira, 2022; Raymond et al., 2022).

Embracing relational values as a third category in environmental ethics does not necessarily mean adopting a relational worldview as described in the previous chapter; but accounting for the significance of relationships between humans and nature is well in line with the respective ideas. We suggest that a broad adoption of relational values can be an important step towards mainstreaming more encompassing relational approaches, which we deem a central element of the Symbiocene.

3. A new mindset for the Symbiocene

At the core of a Symbiocene as we envision it would be a worldview that is no longer anthropocentric and individualistic, but instead relational and humble, embracing the fact that human beings are deeply entangled with each other and with myriads of other living and non-living entities on our planet. This shift would create a deep awareness of the manifold intended and unintended consequences of any activity for other human and non-human beings. In resonance with this perspective, Masao Miyoshi’s critique of globalism proposes a “planetarian” approach that prioritizes the well-being of the planet as a whole over national, ethnic, or anthropocentric concerns (Miyoshi, 2001) (Fig. 1). Currently, planet-centred thinking is not the predominant thinking paradigm. In Figure 1, we suggest that past, prevailing and potential future thinking paradigms can be thought of as progressing from anthropocentric to relational, this progression being related to a change in human-nature relationships from degenerative to regenerative (see also Wahl, 2016).

The anthropocentric worldview in which economic growth is regarded as the main aim for society goes hand in hand with the exploitation of natural resources of all kinds and a degenerative human-nature relationship. The rise of human-centred thinking is based on the insight that leading a full and flourishing life does not only depend on income, but on other factors as well, for example the security and satisfaction derived from work, physical and mental health, social connections, personal and family ties, as well as societal elements such as crime rates, levels of trust, and the quality of public services like health care and

education. None of these facets automatically improves with economic growth, and in many cases can even be compromised by the methods used to generate growth (OECD, 2020). As one manifestation of this thinking paradigm, the discipline of human-centred design emerged, which places people's needs, behaviours, and experiences at the forefront of the design process (Krippendorff, 2004). Since a human-centred view questions the growth paradigm by acknowledging that human needs extend beyond economic gain, it can be expected to lead to design approaches with fewer degenerative effects on the environment. However, this mindset still clearly focusses on humans only. This changes with the rise of the idea that for assuring enduring well-being of people, a depletion of natural resources urgently needs to be prevented. 'Sustainability' became an important concept, dominating thinking in many societal groups and large parts of the world (Purvis et al., 2019). However, as pointed out, e.g., by Indigenous peoples, the concept of sustainability is still connected to the idea of 'taking'. Sustainable resource management has the aim to assure that resources are used in a way that prevents depletion, so that future generations will be able to 'keep taking' (Kimmerer, 2011). Moving to a regenerative mindset, opposed to that, would mean to not only 'take', but also to 'give', thus making it possible to go beyond a neutral towards a positive impact on non-human beings and non-living things (Fig. 1). This view is in line with recent calls to become not only 'carbon-neutral', but also 'nature-positive' (see <https://www.naturepositive.org>).

Figure 1: Trajectory of the transition towards a Symbiocene that leads from anthropocentric, degenerative, to planet-centred, regenerative thinking. Framework concept and visualisation by Ingrid Rügemer, 2023. Licensed under CC BY 4.0. Developed as an original

concept building upon and extending Reed (2006).

The idea of an encompassing, global transition to planet-centred thinking, based on a relational paradigm, and focused on regenerative human-nature relationships may sound promising. But what exactly would that mean? Is that even realistic? And how could it be achieved? The following chapters will suggest answers to these questions.

4. The Symbiocene as a transformative vision

Many recent studies and reports have pointed out that a sweeping transformative change, engaging global society, is the only way to get hold of the diverse crises humanity is currently facing – and that such a change is indeed possible. In their global assessment, the Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services (IPBES) states that the most important leverage point towards transformative change is to “*embrace diverse visions of a good life*” (IPBES, 2019, p. 40). The idea of a good life is deeply rooted in Western philosophy (e.g., Eser, 2016), and is interpreted in the report to mean “*a good quality of life that [does] not entail ever-increasing material consumption*” (IPBES, 2019, p. 17). In follow-up studies, it has been emphasized that such diverse visions of a good life would have to be co-developed locally, to guarantee their match to diverse realities and cultural backgrounds, and to ground them in existing abilities, techniques, and practices (Jahn et al., 2020).

Even though eco-anxiety can trigger action as well (Kurth & Pihkala, 2022), it has been argued that such negative emotions tend to lead to short-term engagement only. For enhancing long-term engagement and transformative action, communication and activities that produce positive emotions have proven much more useful (de Lange et al., 2022). Developing and communicating positive visions of a good life and a regenerative future might therefore be a powerful tool favoring transition (Ellis et al., 2025). Stories full of hope are thought to be especially powerful, motivating people to endure setbacks and to stay engaged even if the transformation towards the envisioned positive future takes time (Mauch, 2019).

Thinking about how to trigger transformative change requires considering different dimensions that can be involved in change, i.e., the personal, social, and planetary dimension (Fig. 2). In each of these dimensions, a transformation can happen with regards to thinking (internal transformation) or acting (external transformation). Encompassing transformative change will need to cover all of these directions and dimensions. Theory says that a fundamental change in thinking, triggered, e.g., by visions of a good life, stories of hope or, as we suggest here, narratives of a Symbiocene, is highly likely to affect acting. Such visions and stories can have the power to access so-called deep leverage points, and thus can have effects much more significant than interventions aiming at external transition only (e.g., taxes and incentives) (Wamsler et al., 2021) (see also Ghirardello & Isetti, 2023). Changes on the personal level, further, can reproduce on the social level, because changes in acting can change social norms and social infrastructure, which will facilitate further progress (Myers & Clayton, 2015). The chances that individuals can have multiplying effects will be strongly enhanced in participatory settings and situations that allow for co-development and co-design. It has therefore been pointed out repeatedly that novel governance approaches are needed that allow for more inclusion and participation (e.g., Collste et al., 2023; van Dijk et al., 2023). An additional advantage of such approaches is that they allow close consideration

of local needs and wishes, an important precondition for developing visions that give hope to a broad range of stakeholders.

Fig. 2: Transformative change is possible if there is an internal as well as external change of thinking as well as acting, including the personal, social as well as planetary dimension. Acting and thinking are connected in a feedback loop. Framework concept and visualisation by Ingrid Rügemer, 2023. Licensed under CC BY 4.0.

We propose that creating visions and narratives about the Symbiocene – a future shaped by humility, planet-centred thinking, and regenerative human–nature relationships – holds the potential to spark transformation across multiple dimensions: from internal to external, from personal to planetary, and from thinking to acting. This narrative, we argue, can open new pathways of imagination and enable diverse, as yet unthinkable, manifestations of a new paradigm. We further suggest that its transformative power is amplified when these stories about the Symbiocene are connected to sensory-triggered experiential encounters.

5. Sensory-triggered experiences as catalysts of change

In the previous sections, we have described the conceptual basis of the idea of a Symbiocene and offered the concept as an umbrella term for the integration of manifold and diverse existing ideas. We will now explore how experiences triggered through sight, sound, touch, taste, and smell can serve as powerful catalysts for deeper reflection and behavioural shifts.

Cognitive processes are inextricably linked with bodily interactions in the environment (Lakoff & Johnson, 1999). For example, it has been shown that in practices such as mindfulness, enhanced sensory awareness is associated with quantifiable alterations in brain structures linked to emotional regulation and self-awareness (Hölzel et al., 2011). From a phenomenological standpoint, sensory experiences are intrinsic to how individuals perceive and comprehend the world and how they interact (Heidegger, 1962; Merleau-Ponty, 1945). The act of encountering the world through the senses allows individuals to pause and reflect

on their place within social systems (Giddens, 1984) and potentially modify their actions (Giddens, 1991). Sensory experiences thus have transformative potential not only with respect to the personal dimension (Fig. 2), but they can also play out in the social dimension, disrupting everyday routines and prompting individuals to reflect on and transform their social actions (Fig. 3). The following section will examine two principal pathways for instigating behavioural change through sensory-triggered experiences: Experiencing nature, and arts interventions.

Fig. 3: Activating change through sensory-triggered experiences. New experiences can trigger cognitive and emotional reactions that can subsequently trigger new ways of thinking, finally leading from established behaviour to behavioural change. This process is especially likely to happen when experiences affect multiple senses and stimulate strong emotions. Framework concept and visualisation by Ingrid Rügemer, 2023. Licensed under CC BY 4.0.

5.1 Nature experiences as catalyst of change

A forest walk, where we smell trees and grass, watch butterflies, listen to crickets and song birds, and by chance observe a deer or squirrel, can trigger many kinds of emotions as, e.g., empathy, awe, or a sense of belonging. It has often been argued that the possibility for experiencing nature, and thus for nourishing a general feeling of connectedness to nature, is one of the keys to happiness, and an essential component of a good life (Eser et al., 2014; Krebs, 2021; Nussbaum, 2000). Also, empirical studies have demonstrated that experience of nature affects attitudes and held values (Cazalis et al., 2023), and that sensory contact with living organisms and ecosystems is positively associated with pro-environmental behaviour (Soga & Gaston, 2024). Unfortunately, however, there is an ongoing loss of opportunities for people to experience nature. As more and more people move into cities, and green spaces in urban and suburban environments become increasingly sparse, the possibilities to interact with any kind of nature become rarer (Cazalis et al., 2023). This “extinction of experience” may have serious consequences for people’s attitudes toward nature (Soga & Gaston, 2016). Importantly, the apparent disconnection from nature is not only happening on an individual, but also on a social level (Beery et al., 2023). Not only is there an extinction of experience, feeling of disconnect etc. at the level of individual people, but there are also political, institutional, or socio-cultural constraints, often reproducing existing inequalities. For example, in cities the lack of access to nature is usually more pronounced in densely populated areas (Zoderer & Hainz-Renetzeder, 2025).

There are many ways to change this situation, and to take actions towards allowing more people to reconnect with nature. Ideally, such actions span the entire continuum from the individual to the social level (Beery et al., 2023). Governmental action could, e.g., lead to the provisioning of better public access to nature experience, by enhancing green spaces in all parts of a city, building bike paths accompanied by tree plantings instead of roads and

highways, and by fostering outdoor activities in schools. Group-based activities in nature seem to be especially well suited to enhance feelings of connectedness to nature (Carr & Hughes, 2023); these kinds of activities could be especially promoted and initialized by local institutions. Recent research also indicates that gardening has the potential to induce a positive ‘noticing nature’ feed-back loop, reversing the negative ‘extinction of experience’ loop (Garfinkel et al., 2024). Motivating citizens to engage in wildlife-friendly gardening could therefore have the double effect of enhancing biodiversity and connectedness of citizens to nature at the same time.

Concerning the individual level, actions towards reconnecting with nature are especially powerful if they stimulate emotions (Ives et al., 2018). In nature reserves and areas with outdoor attractions, it is a common practice to set up information signs and offer tours guided by naturalists. Such activities target cognitive experiences. It has been argued, however, that especially if the aim is to trigger behavioural change and societal transformation, actions have to appeal to the heart and not only to the mind (e.g., Krebs, 2021). In this respect, it would be useful to develop innovative ways for motivating people, e.g., to step from the path into the forest, and to smell, touch, and taste. This could stimulate a ‘sense of wonder’ (Carson, 1956), offering a direct way for enhancing the feeling of connectedness to nature.

Finding new ways for enhancing the possibilities for people to experience nature thus can be a key for moving towards regenerative human-nature relationships. It is in direct, everyday interactions with animals, plants, and other organisms that people could experience the self-willingness of non-human entities in nature on the one hand, and the beneficial as well as negative effects of human activities on the environment on the other. Communicating the significance of emotional approaches to nature is key, and professional nature conservation would be well-advised to move beyond an emphasis of an economic value of nature towards its value as a source for deep and meaningful emotions (see also Leibenath et al., 2021).

5.2 Arts-based experiences as catalyst of change

The term "arts" encompasses diverse creative and expressive disciplines such as visual arts (painting, sculpture, photography), performing arts (theatre, dance, music), literary arts (poetry, prose), and design arts (architecture, various design fields). Form-giving and storytelling are essential to any artistic expression, since they enable the transformation of abstract ideas into concrete forms and narratives. Arts prioritize creativity and aesthetic expression in search of new perspectives on the world. Works of art offer interpretation and meaning-making, and evoke prompt reflection and emotional responses.

Within this broad field, artistic practices often draw on multisensory and affective modes of engagement to explore and communicate meaning. One such approach is embodied sensemaking, which emphasizes the role of the body in processes of learning, reflection, and emotional understanding. Rooted in the principles of embodied cognition, this approach highlights how abstract concepts – in particular emotions – are grounded in bodily experiences and sensorimotor systems. Engaging the body not only enhances emotional engagement but also strengthens memory retention and conceptual understanding. As Niedenthal (2007) argues, emotions are not solely mental states but are experienced and understood through reenactments in the body, which allows individuals to connect more deeply with ideas and issues. Similarly, Johnson (2007) emphasizes that meaning arises from our embodied interactions with the world, grounding abstract thought in sensory and motor experiences. Additionally, embodied sensemaking fosters social change by involving group

participation in artistic practices, promoting shared understanding and collective reflection. Through this interaction, ingrained perspectives can be disrupted, new ways of thinking encouraged, and emotional responses activated. These responses, as Damasio (1994) argues, are not separate from rational thought but are essential to decision-making and meaning-making. We suggest that artistic interventions involving embodied sensemaking are especially promising for inducing transformative change because they deeply engage individuals' physical, emotional, and cognitive systems, making the process of understanding more holistic and impactful.

From a philosophical perspective, the impact of arts-based experiences can be underpinned by the Actor-Network Theory (ANT) developed mainly by Bruno Latour (2005) and the Object-Oriented Ontology (OOO) as suggested by Graham Harman (2018). Both philosophical concepts provide insights into how arts could trigger transformative change. According to Latour (2005), artworks and designed forms become active agents connected in networks with human actors. They influence discourse and behaviour through the meanings they convey and the actions they inspire (Latour, 2005). In contrast, OOO encourages considering the agency of the artworks and design forms themselves. It acknowledges that the objects created during artistic expression have a lasting, autonomous impact on social dynamics and human behaviour. When an artistic form or designed object is linked to a narrative, it not only transmits a human perspective but also functions within its own reality, influencing perceptions, actions and social dynamics beyond its original context. The narrative imbues the object with a life and agency that extends its impact, prompting further engagement and interpretation from those who interact with it (Harman, 2018).

Arts-based experiences can unfold their transformative potential not only through emotions triggered by the work of art itself, but also through involved materials. This notion is the basis for a recent trend in sustainability-focused art and design called New Material Culture. It advocates regenerative material choices and encourages a rethinking of how materials contribute to reducing environmental impact, thereby promoting innovative and responsible use in line with contemporary societal values. New Material Culture explores the interconnectedness between humans, objects and their environments, considering how materials shape social, cultural and environmental realities. This perspective shifts the focus from materials as mere tools to active participants in change, capable of altering human perception, behaviour and social interaction (Bennett, 2010). Particularly in the context of transformation, this engagement facilitates deeper understanding, empathy and reflection (Coole & Frost, 2010). In sustainability-focused art and design practice, the New Material Culture encourages the use of materials not just for function, but as storytellers and agents of change. For example, sustainable design practices that use recycled or bio-based materials not only reduce environmental impact but also challenge existing consumer behaviour and encourage societal change to embrace sustainability (Manzini, 2015).

The forms in which arts-based experiences can trigger emotions that have the potential to induce transformative change thus are manifold. We suggest that this potential is by far not utilized frequently enough, and we call for a more systematic exploration of the potential arts have to offer for conveying the vision of a regenerative future, for stimulating change in mindsets and for triggering respective action.

4. Conclusions

With this contribution, we suggest the recently introduced concept of a Symbiocene as transformative vision for moving towards a regenerative future. We regard the notion of the Symbiocene as aligning well with the aim of ‘living in harmony with nature’ that was recently reinforced in the Global Biodiversity Framework (CBD, 2022). However, while this latter notion seems to suggest that a state of continuously harmonious human-nature interactions can be achieved, the notion of the Symbiocene rather leaves room for the idea that human-nature relationships may take the form of ongoing negotiations, in which the partners are equitable and deeply entangled. Humans here are regarded as constituted by nature and vice versa, and human interactions with nature are characterized by a humble approach and an awareness of the unforeseeable consequences of actions and respective responses (Vucetich et al., 2024). The concept of the Symbiocene in that sense is meant as a contribution towards a revision of existing mindsets. It is meant to set the scene for the development of more and more meaningful narratives about how to move towards a regenerative future.

Fig. 4: Everyone is a designer, because humans have to consume, dispose and build in order to survive. Planet-centred thinking means to move towards a mindset that aims for regenerative effects of our actions for ourselves, our communities and our planet. Framework concept and visualisation by Ingrid Rügemeier, 2023. Licensed under CC BY 4.0.

Above, we discussed how changes in thinking and acting on the personal level may affect the social and planetary dimensions (Fig. 2). This implies that local actions can, over time, lead to significant transformations. In design discourse, this resonates with the well-known notion that *everyone is a designer*, a perspective famously articulated by Herbert A. Simon: “Everyone designs who devises courses of action aimed at changing existing situations into preferred ones” (Simon, 1969, p. 111). Since as humans, we can only exist by consuming,

disposing and building, there is no way around affecting other human and non-human beings as well as the non-living environment. Any action thus comes with a power for shaping the own environment – and this power can very well be used for contributing to a regenerative future (Fig. 4). The vision of a Symbiocene can serve as a guideline for decisions about future actions, on the very local as well as the very global scale.

Author Contributions

Tina Heger and Oliver Szasz developed the line of argument. Both authors reviewed and analysed the literature. Tina Heger led the writing of the manuscript. Both authors contributed critically to the drafts and approved the final version for publication.

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